

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Value Added Course 2020-21 academic year for BPT

BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID

**COLLEGE OF
PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Value Added Course
(online via Zoom)

**BASIC NURSING &
FIRST AID**

**FOR BPT (2020 BATCH)
UNDERGRADUATES**

**Learn Lifesaving Skills
From the Experts**

Course Duration: 40 hours

CONTACT
College of Physiotherapy, Ground floor, Srinivas
University City campus, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru
Phone: 0824-2429139
Email: deanphysiotherapy@srinivasuniversity.edu.in
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Course period	From January 2021 till March 2021, during 1 st semester (10 weeks)
Duration	40 hours (4 hours/week)
Language of instruction	English
Participants	BPT 1 st year undergraduates (2020 batch)

Course Objectives:

- Understand the new responsibilities of an Occupational First Aider.
- To be familiar with health & safety legislation on first aid in the workplace (e.g. Contents of First Aid Box)

Course Outcomes:

A successful completion of this course will enable students to:

- ✓ Define and select an appropriate treatment to minimize the consequences of injury until the arrival of medical assistance.
- ✓ Demonstrate appropriate treatment for an injury which does not require the attention of a medical practitioner or nurse.
- ✓ Plan health & safety measures on first aid in the workplace.

Course Outline:

Week	Lectures	Assignments	Hour ¹
Module 1 «Introduction to nursing and nursing positions»			
1-2	What is nursing? Nursing principles. Inter personnel relationships. Basic turns: Bandaging extremities: Triangular Bandages and their application. Nursing position: Environment safety: Bed making, prone, lateral, dorsal, dorsal recumbent, Flower's positions, comfort measures, Aids and rest and sleep.	Home assignments Lab: Practice of nursing positions	8
Module 2 «Bedside management and methods of Nourishment»			
3-5	Bed side Management: Giving and taking Bed pan, Urinal: Observation of stools, Urine. Observation of Sputum, Understand use and care of care of catheters, enema giving Lifting and transporting patients: Lifting patient up in the bed, transferring from bed to wheel chair, transferring from bed to stretcher Methods of giving Nourishment: Feeding, tube feeding, Tube feeding, drips, transfusion. Observation of surgical procedures	Assignments Lab: Practice sessions	12
Module 3 «First Aid»			

6-7	Importance of first aid in physiotherapy Instrumentation used in First Aid (First Aid kit) Examination of Vital signs.	Home Assignments Lab: Demonstrations and practice	8
Module 4 «First Aid procedures»			
8-10	First Aid in cardiac arrest and in Respiratory failure First Aid in Burns, Electric shock, Hypovolemic shock and Drowning First Aid in Spinal cord injuries; Poisoning; RTA	Demonstrations and case studies	12

¹ Hours designed for Classroom sessions, video tutorials, Home Assignments, Activities etc.

Attendance Policy

The course requires compulsory 75% attendance and only in this case a student will be issued a certificate.

Book References:

1. I Clement. Text book on First Aid & Emergency Nursing. Jaypee Brothers.
2. N.N Yalayaswamy. First Aid & Emergency Nursing, CBS publishers.
3. Indian First Aid manual. 7th ed. St. John. Ambulance Association, 2017.
4. Glassey N. Physiotherapy for burns & Reconstruction. Wiley, 2004.
5. Harris N. First Aid and Emergency care, AITBS Publishers.
6. Golwalla A. F. Golwalla S. K. A handbook of emergencies, Jaypee Brothers.

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CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

A MOHAMMAD ADHIL

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Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

SOWJANYA

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2021 till March 2021

Total Hours- 40 (Hybrid mode)

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'S. Rajasekar'.

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